

Publication Venues

#	Publication Venue	Type	# of Studies
1	International Journal on Software Tools for Technology Transfer	Journal	1
2	Computer Science-Research and Development	Journal	1
3	Future Generation Computer Systems	Journal	1
4	ICT Express	Journal	1
5	IEEE Symposium on Service-Oriented System Engineering (SOSE)	Conference	2
6	International Conference on Services Computing (SCC)	Conference	2
7	Annual Computer Software and Applications Conference (COMPSAC)	Conference	2
8	Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)	Conference	2
9	International Conference on Software Testing, Verification and Validation (ICST)	Conference	1
10	International Conference on Software Architecture (ICSA)	Conference	1
11	International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE)	Conference	1
12	International Conference on Software Engineering and Formal Methods (SEFM)	Conference	1
13	International Conference on Web Research (ICWR)	Conference	1
14	International Convention on Information and Communication Technology, Electronics and Microelectronics (MIPRO)	Conference	1
15	International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS)	Conference	1
16	International Symposium on Modeling, Analysis, and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems (MASCOTS)	Conference	1
17	International Conference on Information Integration and Web-based Applications and Services (IIWAS)	Conference	1
18	International Conference on Product-Focused Software Process Improvement (PROFES)	Conference	1
19	International Conference on Business Process Modeling, Development and Support (BPMDS)	Conference	1
20	International Conference on Advances in ICT for Emerging Regions (ICTER)	Conference	1
21	International Conference on Reliable Software Technologies (ICRST)	Conference	1
22	International Symposium on Applied Computational Intelligence and Informatics (SACI)	Conference	1
23	International Conference on Computer Applications and Information Processing Technology (CAIPT)	Conference	1
24	International Conference on Cloud Computing and Big Data Analysis (ICCCBDA)	Conference	1

25	International Conference on Software Testing, Verification and Validation Workshops (ICSTW)	Workshop	1
26	International Conference on Software Architecture Companion (ICSA-C)	Workshop	1
27	Software Engineering and Formal Methods Workshop (SEFMW)	Workshop	1